

A Review on Thermal Properties of Aluminium Metal Matrix Composites

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ABSTRACT:

The Aluminum Metal Matrix Composites (AMMCs) have been becoming suitable materials for many devices in the application of various fields like heavy equipment's industry, automobile, aeronautics and etc. because of its excellent physical and structural characteristics. The research on AMMC dealt the effect of reinforcement such as fly-ash, SiC, Al₂O₃, Graphite, B₄C, Cubic Boron Nitride (CBN), TiC, on aluminium in different percentages. Every reinforcement has its own characteristics that enhance the base aluminium characteristics when added. By adding these types of reinforcement to metal base led to enhance the properties like wear resistance, stiffness, creep, tensile strength, fatigue, toughness, thermal conductivity, hardness in comparison with traditional approach on materials engineering. This review paper was aimed to give the detailed information about the impact of various reinforcements incorporated in matrix by illustrating its benefits and drawbacks. This extensive survey on AMMC could be useful to develop farther.

INTRODUCTION:

Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) are the composites of a material with a minimum of two components, one should essentially be a metal, another one could be a different metal like compound or ceramics. They are formed by distributing the reinforcement materials within the matrix. By the introduction of reinforcements like B₄C, SiC, Al₂O₃ to matrix alloy, much useful properties of alloy matrix like hardness,

thermal conductivity, strength, wear-rate and so on would be enhanced. Composite's properties rely upon the properties of particle's phases, its relative quantity, distributed phase geometry in addition to the shape, size and alignment with matrix.

In our daily life, AMMCs have found many applications. AMMCs are composites that only use aluminium as the matrix and incorporate a few reinforced components into the matrix. There are a few benefits such as low Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE), improved stiffness, greater hardness and strength, light weight, high specific modulus, enhanced damping capabilities, enhanced wear-resistance and greater Thermal Conductivity (TC) when the reinforced is used in matrix. The matrix may include reinforcing elements in a manner of continuous fibers, particulates or monofilaments. They have been used in the fields of industrial goods, automotive and aeronautics applications. The reinforcement particulates must be robust, flexible and anti-reactive in the specified operating temperature. SiC, Al₂O₃, graphite, Cubic Boron Nitride (CBN) are commonly used as reinforcements.

In order to gain the optimum properties, selection of good reinforcement and the matrix materials are not only sufficient, processing method also plays a significant role. There are different techniques available to produce AMMCs like powder metallurgy, squeeze casting, stir casting, chemical vapour deposition, pressure infiltration etc. Among these manufacturing techniques stir casting is the prevalent technique which has been used by many investigators since the process is cost-effective, and this process have greater hardness and refined micro structure grains than other techniques.

Thermal Properties of MMCs

The material's thermal properties were those features which are associated with its heat conductivity. In another sentence, when heat moves through it, substances possess these properties. Thermal-resistivity or conductivity, thermal-expansion coefficient, thermal diffusivity and specific-heat capacity were few of essential properties of thermal. The evaluation and characterization of this kind of properties plays crucial

role. The investigation and observation of thermal properties are conducted at elevated temperature, room-temperature too.

Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE)

CTE is described as Change in dimensions of material accompanying with alteration in the temperature. In automobile applications temperature variations occur so that less CTE substances recommended.

Thermal conductivity(TC)

Thermal Conductivity (TC) is the material's property that depicts the capacity for heat conductivity. The following paragraphs briefs the latest inventions in thermal properties such as thermal conductivity and coefficient of thermal expansion of AMC's which are developed through various production techniques.

V.S.N. Venkataramana [1] et al (2020), In this present study, aluminium base alloy (LM9) is reinforced with multi walled carbon nano tubes (MWCNTs). The tests are conducted to evaluate for thermal behaviour under varying temperature, and thermal conductivity to assess the influence of MWCNTs as reinforcements. The mixed composition of MWCNTs is 1%, 2% and 3%. There is no change in thermal behaviour of the composites under varying temperature conditions. The thermal analyser showed a marginal reduction in the thermal conductivity due to increase in density of microstructure and resulting improved hardness.

Fig. 1: FESEM micrograph of **a** LM9 Aluminium, **b** Aluminium+1% MWCNTs, **c** Aluminium+2% MWCNTs, **d** Aluminium+3% MWCNTs

Sunil Kumar Reddy [2] et al (2021), the objective of the research is to assess the thermal and mechanical properties of the aluminium metal matrix composites when reinforced with ceramics like fly ash, silicon carbide, tungsten carbide, boron carbide, fired bricks. The mixed composition of graphite is 3%, 6%, 9% and 12% and fly ash being constant 10%. The outcome of the research is thermal conductivity and coefficient of thermal expansion varying temperature ranges from 50-300 degree C reduces with increase in

wt% of the graphite content. The composite tensile strength and hardness improved with the wt% of graphite improved upto 9% and then decreased.

Fig. 2: Thermal conductivity vs Temperature of Al7475/Fly Ash/Gr

Fig. 2; CTE vs Temperature for the Al7475/Fly Ash/Gr

Alberto Torres Miranda [3] et al (2018), the research study is aluminium matrix composites reinforced with cu-coated pitch based carbon fibers (Al/cu-CFs) were fabricated using a novel combination of rheo casting and equal channel angular extrusion techniques. In order to exploit the thermal conductivity of material. The results are the composites with highest degree of fiber alignment shows a thermal conductivity improvement of 20% with respect to rheocast composites. The improvement is due to porosity reduction, improved fiber alignment and forced intimate contact of clean CF surface with the matrix.

M. Kannanb [4] et al (2020), the research is to study the thermal and mechanical behaviour of aluminium based hybrid metal matrix composites with varying reinforcement of graphite and 10% of silicon carbide. The graphite % used is 3%, 6% and 9% and 10% of SiC. The results obtained are coefficient of thermal expansion and thermal conductivity of hybrid MMCs with varying temperature from 50-300 degree C decreased as increasing of graphite reinforcement with 10wt% SiC. The hardness and tensile strength of hybrid MMCs increased as graphite % increased with 10wt% of SiC.

M. Polok-Rubinić [5] et al (2020), the research is to present the modern manufacturing methods of production and compare the thermal properties of composite materials with aluminium alloy matrix reinforced by Al₂O₃ particles. The wt% of reinforcement material is 5%, 10% and 15%. In results they observed that the addition of Al₂O₃ particles has influences on thermal properties of composites. Linear thermal expansion coefficient decreases with addition of reinforcement material.

Arundee Murugan [6] et al (2019), in this research aluminium metal matrix is reinforced with zirconium oxide and graphite materials. In the composition the aluminium is 80% and ZrO is 15% and Gr is 5%. The results obtained are increased thermal and mechanical properties over other two composite materials such as increased hardness and tensile strength.

Xiaopeng Han [7] et al (2018), in this research aluminium metal matrix is reinforced with Cu particles with nanotube, Ag coated Gr flakes and films, urea and starch were mixed to fabricate porous performs. In the

result the composition exhibited high thermal conductivity with graphite film, and there is increase in excellent bending strength.

Fig. 3: The TC of the composites with different graphite film.

Jagadeesh. N [8] et al (2018), the aim of the research work is to fabricate hybrid nano composite material containing Al6061, reinforcements of SiC, ZrO₂ and Gr. For each sample they increased 0.75% of reinforcements. In the result they observed that the thermal conductivity decreases with the increase in reinforcement and hardness of the composites were significantly improved by the presence of reinforcement content and also tensile strength increases as well as decreases with enlarged amount of reinforcements.

Raj Kumar [9] et al (2021), in this study Al6061 based metal matrix composites reinforced with Ni, Cr, graphene and Mg to improve thermal conductivity. The results revealed that thermal conductivity of fabricated composites increases with Ni, Cr, Mg and graphene nano particles. With further expansion of reinforced particles of Ni and Cr, the thermal conductivity decreases. Finite element analysis has been conducted to determine the thermal gradient, thermal flux using experimental values such as density, thermal conductivity, specific heat and enthalpy at various temperature ranges to validate the experimental results. M. Penchal Reddy [10] et al (2018), in the present work nanosized TiC reinforced with aluminium

metal matrix composites. The TiC content used is 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 vol%. To obtain the microstructural, mechanical and thermal properties. The result obtained are tensile and compressive strength of aluminium composites increases with increase in TiC content, while ductility decreases. The coefficient of thermal expansion decreases with the progressive addition of TiC nano particles.

Fig. 4: Comparison of experimental CTE with theoretical prediction for Al-TiC nano composites as function of Ti C content

S. Kushnoore [11] et al (2019), in the present study the thermal behaviour of pure Al6061 and fly ash reinforced Al6061 with varying particulate sizes were investigated for the first time. The reinforcement content used here is 4%-16%, and the fly ash particulates size is 50nanometers and 51-100nanometers respectively. In results it has been observed for all cases the accumulation of fly ash in Al6061 decreases the thermal conductivity and increases the specific heat carrying capacity of a hybrid composite. Increase in wt% of fly ash in Al6061 decreases thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity respectively.

Peter Nyanor [12] et al (2020), in the present study the aluminium matrix reinforced with carbon nano tubes (CNT), micron-sized Ti C particles, and bimodal(nano + micron) hybrid Ti C-CNT is fabricated to improve

the mechanical properties and reduce thermal expansion. In the result the hardness value of bimodal TiC-CNT reinforced Al composite is significantly higher than monomodal TiC composite. Coefficient of thermal expansion reduces with CNT and TiC addition but is even significantly better in the hybrid reinforced composition.

Fig. 5:CTE of pure Al, CNT/Al, TiC/Al and hybrid TiC–CNT/Al composites measured from 150 °C to 350 °C

Fig. 6: Comparison between experimental measurement and theoretical calculation of CTE for CNT, TiC and hybrid reinforced Al matrix composites

S. Jacob [13] et al (2017), the present study states a reduction of the CTE (Coefficient of Thermal Expansion) values is perceived as the graphite composition is increased with 10% of Fly-Ash. The vindication for the reduced in the Co. Thermal Expansion values could be accredited to the much lower CTE value of Gr. when compared to that of the AMMC and Fly-Ash.

S.A. Mohana Krishna [14] et al (2016) in their research they added graphite and SiC with aluminium metal matrix composite and they observed that thermal conductivity is improved by the addition of graphite into the aluminium and sic mixture.

S. Jacob [15] et al (2017) Thermal analysis on Al7075/Al₂O₃ metal matrix composites fabricated by stir casting process. A reduction of the CTE (Coefficient of Thermal Expansion) values is perceived as the graphite composition is increased with 10% of Fly-Ash. The vindication for the reduced in the Co. Thermal

Expansion values could be accredited to the much lower CTE value of Gr. when compared to that of the AMMC and Fly-Ash.

H.C. Anil Kumar [16] et al (2011) As the temperature is increased, the CTE of the AMMC is also observed to be increased. The maximum CTE value achieved at 10 wt.% of FlyAsh and 3wt% of Graphite at 300°C and Low-value of the CTE which is $(5.24 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C})$ is evinced for 3 wt.% of Gr. with 10 weight% of Fly-Ash at 50°C.

A.M.Razzaq [17] et al (2011) A reduction in the thermal conductivity (TC), thermal-diffusivity and sp. heat values of Aluminium7475/Fly-Ash/Gr Al-MMCs were noticed as the composition of graphite is increased with 10 wt.% of Fly-Ash.

S.Sundaram [18] et al (2011) The thermal conductivity of the AMMCs is escalated as the temperature increases. The maximum thermal conductivity value is 135 w/m-k was achieved at 300°C with Al7475 with reinforcements 12wt%Gr and 10wt%flyash due to more Graphite, it increases thermal energy.

Wang [19] et al (2016) the paper was a research on Silver Nanoparticle-Deposited Boron Nitride Nanosheets as Fillers for Polymeric Composites with High Thermal Conductivity, The thermal conductivity of the composite is significantly increased from 1.63 W/m-K for the composite filled with the silver nanoparticle-deposited boron nitride nanosheets to 3.06 W/m-K at the boron nitride nanosheets loading of 25.1 vol %.

WangH. W. [20] et al (2014) Fabrication, interface characterization and modelling of oriented graphite flakes/Si/Al composites for thermal management applications. With increasing volume fraction of Gf from 13.7 to 71.1 vol%, the longitudinal (i.e. parallel to the graphite layers) TC of the composites increased from 179 to 526 W/m K, while the longitudinal CTE decreased from 12.1 to 7.3 ppm/K.

Amy. MMarconnet, [21] et al (2017) In Investigation of aluminum foams and graphite fillers for improving the thermal conductivity of paraffin wax-based phase change materials, Thermal and Thermomechanical Phenomena in Electronic Systems (ITherm), The thermal conductivity of the EG/paraffin composites increases respectively to the volume percent of expanded graphite. While the thermal conductivity increased, there is some negative impact on latent heat storage compared to pure paraffin wax.

Molina, [22] et al (2017) Porosity Effect on Thermal Properties of Al-12 wt % Si/Graphite Composites materials. Highly irregular graphite particles were used to fabricate the preforms. The thermal conductivity of these composites gradually increases with the applied infiltration pressure given the inherent reduction in porosity.

Wang C [23] et al (2016) investigated on the influence of carbide coating on the thermal conductivity and flexural strength of X (X = SiC, TiC) coated graphite/Al composites. SiC coating on the GF and the reduction of particle size increase the thermal conductivity and flexural strength. Compared with the raw GF/Al composites, the thermal conductivity of the SiC coated GF/Al composites increases from 610 to 633 $W(m K)^{-1}$ when the volume fraction of GF reaches 70 vol% and the particle size of Al is about 20 μm . And the thermal conductivity of 70 vol% SiC GF/Al composites approaches 704 $W(mK)^{-1}$, when the size of Al powder decreases to 1 μm . TiC coating on the GF greatly increases the flexural strength of the composites, but decreases the thermal conductivity sharply. The bending strength of TiC-coated GF/Al composites approaches 103 MPa when the particle size of Al is about 1 μm , when the volume fraction of GF is 50 vol%.

Xue, C. [24] et al (2016) the paper research held on the thermal conductivity and mechanical properties of flake graphite/Al composite with a SiC nano-layer on graphite surface. The thermal conductivity of the graphite-SiC/Al composite in x-y plane direction increased from 528 to 735 $W/m K$ as the volume fraction of the graphite increased from 40 to 70%. The introduction of nano SiC layer indeed improved the interfacial thermal conductance and thus increased the thermal conductivity of the composites.

Rouhi s. [25] et al (2017) their paper work on Finite element investigation into the thermal conductivity of carbon nanotube/aluminum nanocomposites. It is shown that the best enhancement in the thermal conductivity of aluminum matrix occurs by the regular distribution of the nanotubes along the temperature change. Also, increasing the volume fraction of nanotubes in aluminum matrix leads to increasing the thermal conductivity coefficient of the nanocomposite.

Yang, Y. [26] et al (2016) they conducted a research on the interfacial characteristic, thermal conductivity, and modelling of graphite flakes/Si/Al composites by vacuum gas pressure infiltration. As a result, the composites with graphite volume fraction of 17.4–69.4% sintered at 655 °C/45 MPa for 100 min exhibit in-plane thermal conductivities of 380–940 W/mK, over 90% of the predictions by rule of mixture. These composites possess higher in-plane thermal conductivities than graphite flake/aluminum composites due to well-controlled graphite orientation and fabrication parameters, which indicates that these composites are promising materials for effective thermal management.

WagihA. [27] et al (2016). Their research was held on the Effect of Mg Addition on Mechanical and Thermoelectrical Properties of Al-Al₂O₃ Nanocomposite. The coefficient of thermal expansion and electrical conductivity were reduced. Interestingly, increasing GNPs content has almost negligible effect of the thermal conductivity, at which the thermal conductivity is slightly reduced by a factor of 5% only by increasing GNPs content to 1.2%. These results highlight the advantage of reinforcing Cu-Al₂O₃ nanocomposites by GNPs coated Ag for manufacturing hybrid nanocomposite with improved mechanical properties and good thermal conductivity.

Hari Chandran R [28] et al (2022), their investigation was about experimental and numerical evaluation of thermal conductivity of graphene nanoplatelets reinforced aluminium composites produced by powder metallurgy and hot extrusion techniques, the thermal conductivity of GNPs dispersed aluminium composites are increases with increasing in the weight% of GNPs.

Shihao Zhang [29] et al (2022), the research was about micro structure and thermal properties of binary ceramic particle-reinforced aluminium matrix composites with SiC/LAS, the composites achieved a low CTE at 500 degrees by increasing the LAS consequently.

Ning Wei [30] et al (2022), the investigation on thermal conductivity of aluminium/graphene metal matrix composites from the thermal boundary conductance to thermal regulation. The thermal conductivity of Gr/Al MMCs increases with the increase in Graphene components and doubles at its volume fraction of 40%.

CONCLUSIONS:

The aim of this review is to study the effect of thermal properties with the addition of various reinforcements to aluminium. The following facts were revealed by the various researchers on AMC's. Thermal conductivity and CTE of AMC's varies according to the reinforcements and its sizes. As the size of the reinforcements reduces there is a clear enhancement in thermal properties have been noted. Thermal properties are also depends on operating temperature. Thermal conductivity and CTE of composites found to be increased with operating temperature. With the inclusion of TiC to aluminium alloy CTE of composites reduces by a significant amount.

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